

CONCEPT-STROKE

Effectiveness and efficiency of the care pathway followed by acute ischemic stroke patients, using real world data.

Key words

Acute ischemic stroke; care pathway; effectiveness; process mining; Spain

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Version

Version	Description
1.0.0	First draft of protocol
1.1.0	Updated protocol with information on final participant regions

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Study rationale

Background

Stroke burden

Stroke is the second cause of death in the general population with a gender gap against the female population, representing the first cause of disability. Worldwide, Stroke accounts for an estimated death toll of 6.7 million people dying (430,000 in EU) [1], approximately the 11.9% of the overall death toll (8% in EU); for those survivors, the 44% endure functional dependency responsible of the 6.8% of the Disability-Adjusted Life Years in Europe [2].

Particularly in Spain, although the mortality rate has been decreasing since 2000 with a 25.69 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in 2016 [3], the 7.1% of all deaths were yet due to stroke in 2016, between 26,209 and 33,330 depending on the estimations [4]. The impact of stroke on families' working and social conditions is high because of the heavy economic burden that implies.

Stroke Care

In the last two decades, significant advances in both prevention (e.g., control of cardiovascular disease risk factors, monitoring and treatment of atrial fibrillation [5]) and acute treatment of ischaemic strokes (i.e. reperfusion using intravenous fibrinolysis [6], mechanical thrombolysis [7] or both [8]) have changed the expectations on stroke outcomes, both in terms of survival and disability.

Nonetheless, to get the most out of the advantages of these new treatments on ischemic stroke, time-to-care is a major issue, as reperfusion therapies for acute treatment are based on a rather short window of opportunity that maximizes the compromise between the resilience of the ischemic brain tissue and the tradeoff between reperfusion and hemorrhage. Health systems have evolved to acknowledge this "time is brain" aphorism [9] organising preferential paths to provide these effective therapies 'in time' to those eligible patients. Indeed, the implementation of organizational changes aiming to configure more effective stroke care have seemingly been leading to a fair decrease in mortality and associated disability [10] [11].

Aware of the need of coordination in the equitable and effective management of stroke patients, the Inter-Territorial Council of the Spanish Healthcare System (CISNS) mandated the design and implementation of the National Strategy for Stroke [2]. The Autonomous Communities assumed the objectives of the National Strategy and implemented twin regional plans with special emphasis on the assistance of acute ischemic stroke, namely Code Stroke. For instance, the region of Aragon implemented the Code Stroke program in 2009, establishing the pathway of care and involving the means to reach full regional coverage of reperfusion therapy using fibrinolysis within the treatment window of opportunity, using all the public hospitals within the regional organization. Similar to Aragon (1.34 million lives, 9 public hospitals), several regions like Navarre (642,797 lives, 4 public hospitals), and the Basque Country (2.16 million lives, 12 public hospitals)

participating in the CONCEPT-Stroke project, implemented their own Code Stroke plans adjusting the national guidelines to their organizational characteristics.

Since 2010, all the regional Health Systems have further deepened their Code Stroke plans setting up reference hospitals for the provision of acute mechanical thrombolysis in eligible patients, and priority flows where the nearest hospital provides fibrinolysis before transferring out to the reference site. Moreover, they also further developed care sub-processes within the main paths; so, a) acute hospital emergency ward assistance to speed up the differential diagnosis (i.e. ischemic, hemorrhage, TIA or nonspecific); b) full regional coverage of neurointerventionism (i.e. providing 365/24/7 stroke assessment and delivery of mechanical thrombolysis); and, c) assessment and early rehabilitation therapy during the hospital admission and immediately after discharge [12]. Several regions have also implemented eHealth initiatives, as ‘Tele-Stroke’ [13], connecting primary care medical doctors with their peers at the hospital, easing access to expert assessment on dubious cases, and enhancing capacity in those doctors who act as first point of assistance in remoter areas.

Relevance of the evaluation of Stroke Care

Along with the development and implementation of Code Stroke programs, the evidence of variations in the use of reperfusion therapies and health outcomes has been gaining instrumental relevance in the assessment of the maturity and effectiveness of stroke action plans. For instance, complementary to regional Code Stroke implementation assessments prior to program updates [12] [14], studies using a National Health System perspective have shown important differences in hospitalizations due to stroke, and in the utilization of reperfusion therapies among regions [3]. Even wider between-hospital differences have been reported when comparing adjusted in-hospital mortality rates after stroke [15], suggesting that organizational differences and coordination flaws between outpatient (i.e. emergency care transportation) and inpatient care make a difference. In turn, evidence showed that a proper management of stroke patients might lead to a mortality risk reduction as large as 45% [16].

On a different line, the increasing knowledge on individual predictors of endovascular treatment success [17] [18] [19], and de facto use of fibrinolysis and mechanical endovascular thrombolysis as standard therapy, are leading the upgrade of guidelines (for example, to widen the window of opportunity for treatment [20]) that implicitly entails setting new processes and changes in the organization that will require future assessment.

The action plan for stroke in Europe, 2018-2030, echoing those concerns, has recently provided guidance on how to develop further National Strategies on Stroke. [21] The action plan’s overarching statement, point out to the need of ‘guiding national stroke care upon evidence-based pathways, sufficiently understood by

the population and adapted to ensure equal access irrespective of patient characteristics, covering the entire chain of care with stroke services regularly audited to promote continuous quality improvement over time. In that sense, the action plan has advocated a research agenda to a) identifying the most relevant barriers to the implementation of evidence-based stroke care and establishing the role of the economic aspects of this implementation; b) measuring the health-economic impact of strokes and return of investment in stroke care at health system level; c) defining the key elements to improve the organization of the stroke care in regions both in terms of health outcomes and cost-effectiveness contributing to the sustainability of the health systems; d) estimating the optimum number and ratios of stroke care centers and stroke units to provide access to effective therapies for all the population; and, e) effectively developing regional networks of emergency medical services (EMS), stroke units and rehabilitation centers to increase survival and improve patient's autonomy after the advent of an acute stroke. CONCEPT-STROKE research outcomes are expected to address all of those research priorities in the Action Plan 2018-2030.

Use of real world data (RWD) to inform health policy and prompt action

Becomes conspicuous that the challenges posed with the implementation and assessment of the national and regional strategies on Stroke require the reutilization of data routinely collected by the health care organizations. What policy-makers need to improve stroke care is to understand how real patients are treated by real organizations in real contexts

The evidence-based policy approach based on using randomized clinical trials and systematic reviews to inform decisions is being observed to transition towards an evidence-based policy paradigm where real life data will ideally generate higher value. This idea has been nicely developed by the Institutes of Medicine that have proposed the development of learning health systems as systems in which 'science, informatics, incentives, and culture are aligned for continuous improvement and innovation, where [...] new knowledge is captured as an integral by-product of the delivery experience'. [22] Indeed umbrella organizations, in particular the OECD, are strongly advocating the reuse of collected data with a view to improve health and healthcare [23]. In turn, the European Commission, as executive body, recognizes as well the reuse of data as one of the pillars for the resilience of our health systems (see details here https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/healthcare/docs/com2014_215_final_en.pdf and here <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/news/eu-task-force-ehealth-redesigning-health-europe-2020>). Some good examples of the reuse of data, where the development of large-scale distributed infrastructures is used in comparative effectiveness and cost effectiveness policy-oriented research, are: the FDA Mini Sentinel on surveillance of adverse events in marketed drugs, the PCORNet on patient outcomes assessment, or the ESPnet on public health surveillance. [24]

Hypothesis

The analytical side of our proposal aims at challenging the following overall null hypothesis: short term and long-term outcomes in Stroke care are not fundamentally influenced by the care path followed by a patient with an ischemic event, nor the multiple decisions made in the pathway of care from the admission to a hospital emergency room onwards.

Specifically: a) we hypothesize that patients enduring an acute ischemic stroke will follow those care pathways that perfectly match their health needs; so that, based on their clinical features, no uncertainty will be observed in the decision processes that leads a patient to one or another path; and, b) consequently, health outcomes and efficiency will be independent of the path followed by the patients

Objectives

General objective: Overall, our proposal aims at estimating the effectiveness and efficiency of the care pathway followed by acute ischemic stroke patients, using real world data routinely collected by five health care systems in Spain, Aragon, Basque Country, and Navarre.

Specific objectives:

- 1) Discovering the actual care pathway of Acute Ischemic Stroke, from the admission to an emergency room in a public hospital to the appearance of an event of interest after discharge;
- 2) Comparing that care pathway with the theoretical pathway that a patient should follow according to the regional stroke plans;
- 3) Out of the analysis of care decisions, eliciting the underlying reasons that lead a patient to follow a particular care path;
- 4) Estimating the differences in health outcomes between care paths;
- 5) Estimating the differences in costs between care paths;
- 6) Analyzing the impact of specific care interventions within and across care paths, in terms of patients' survival; in particular, the comparison between patients receiving thrombectomy alone, those receiving thrombectomy and fibrinolysis, those receiving fibrinolysis alone, and those receiving no treatment;
- 7) Estimating the efficiency of specific interventions within and across care pathways (along with SESCS)
- 8) For specific vulnerable groups (e.g., women, elderly women, less-affluent individuals), carrying out subgroup analyses on the impact of specific care interventions within and across care paths in terms of patients' survival and estimate their efficiency;
- 9) In the specific case of Aragon, the impact of the enlargement of the window of opportunity will be also tested in terms of changes in patients' functional capacities.

Instrumental objectives

- 10) Developing the analytical pipeline for all the CONCEPT projects (see preface);
- 11) Testing methodologies aiming at predicting care paths and health outcomes (along with Navarrabiomed)

Methodology

Study design and context

The study design is an observational and retrospective, CONCEPT-STROKE builds on a two-stage design. First, objectives '1 to 5' will develop on a cross-sectional data mining design, while objectives '6 to 9' will develop on a quasi-experimental differences in differences (comparing four alternatives) and a quasi-experimental ex-ante ex-post design using an historical control (analyzing the enlargement of the timespan window for thrombectomy). The cohort of study will be composed of virtually all individual patients that endured an acute ischemic stroke and were admitted to an emergency room in any acute care public hospitals serving in Aragon, Basque Country, and Navarre since 2010 until 31-12-2022.

Variable and data sources

In the **cross-sectional data mining approach**, two intermediate outputs will be sought; so, a) the pathway of care followed by ischemic stroke patients in each region; and, b) the underlying characteristics that lead a patient to follow a specific path within the pathway measured as a score of propensity for each individual patient. In the case of the pathway of care, the process discovery exercise (see below) will use as variables of interest the various contacts with the care provider (e.g., visiting the triage unit, receiving fibrinolysis, getting a CT scan), as well as the timestamps for every contact (e.g., minute/ hour/day when the contact took place). In the case of the underlying features that lead a patient to follow a specific path, the decision mining analysis (see below) will use as variables of interest demographic characteristics (age, sex, socioeconomic status) and registered clinical features informing on the baseline risk of the patients (e.g., type of ischemic stroke, stroke severity, concurrent comorbidities, and complications).

In the **quasi-experimental approach**, the main endpoints of interest will be patients' survival at 1 year after admission to an emergency room. In addition, the functional status of the patient at discharge and at 6 months after hospital discharge, measured in terms of changes in the modified Rankin Scale (mRS) will be used for the region of Aragon if sufficient data is available on this measurement. mRS measures the degree of disability in daily life activities for people who have suffered a stroke. The scale ranges from 0 no symptoms to 6 death, going across different grades of disability.[25] As Rankin scale is not codified in the usual taxonomies (ICD9th, ICD10th, CIAP) we will retrieve this information using natural language processing (NLP), specifically the annotation guide that is being developed in the context of IctusNet (<http://ictusnet-sudoe.eu/en/>) and the National Plan for the advancement of the Language Technology

(<http://www.agendadigital.gob.es/Paginas/index.aspx>) and validated by our team. The annotation guide will be applied to the discharge reports and to the electronic health records of primary care. Note that this endpoint will serve as a proof of concept for the other partners in CONCEPT-STROKE, with a view to pilot the feasibility of including NLP in future decision mining and effectiveness analyses.

The main exposure variable will be the path discovered in the mining approach; in particular, those paths where patients received thrombectomy alone, those with thrombectomy plus fibrinolysis, those with fibrinolysis alone, and those where patients get no treatment. Concurrent exposures and confounders: Within each path, variables of interest will be: a) Patient level variables: propensity score built in the decision mining analyses, overall time of exposure, new concurrent diagnoses derived from the assistance, interventions (diagnostic, pharmacological or surgical interventions); b) hospital level features including volume of care and type of stroke-related services provided (basic assistance, second level care, reference site) and the health care system (i.e., autonomous community) where the patient is treated. With a view to control selection biases, distance from the place of residence to the hospital of admission will be used as instrumental variable. A detail of the data model (variables and data sources of origin) can be found here <https://github.com/cienciadedatosysalud/CONCEPT-STROKE>.

Sources of information

The analysis requires the secondary use of individual level data from health system users' databases (*i.e., patient administrative information*) or data from Electronic Health Records (EHR, *i.e., emergency care, primary care, hospital admission*). All data sources contains routinely collected data both from healthcare or public health information systems. For the variables required for the study, we refer to the common data model specification published in GitHub (<https://github.com/cienciadedatosysalud/CONCEPT-STROKE>). All this patient information collected in the various health databases will be linked using unique pseudonyms at individual level.

Each region (Aragon, Basque Country, and Navarre) will pull the data from their respective data sources conditional on data availability and access.

Participants

For each participant region, CONCEPT STROKE will use individual pseudonymised linked data from data collected and curated by the corresponding health authorities in the region. Data sources included in this project will be: administrative data from the population in the insured database, clinical and administrative data from the emergency departments, clinical and administrative data from hospital discharges, clinical and administrative data from primary electronic medical records, clinical and administrative data from

pharmaceutical prescriptions and dispensations, drugs reimbursement claims, radiologic digitalized information, and episodes in the corresponding regional stroke registry. See detail on the coverage of this sources in <https://github.com/cienciadedatosysalud/CONCEPT-STROKE>.

Analysis plan

Once the Acute Ischemic Stroke cohort is defined out of the linkage of the data sources just detailed, archetypical steps in process mining (PM) will be: 1) the generation of the event log (basic data structure for the analyses), 2) the process discovery modelling; and 3) the conformance checking and the decision mining analyses. There will be a fourth step in CONCEPT-STROKE, beyond the usual scope of process mining, which is the application of PM outputs to the analysis of comparative effectiveness and efficiency.

The **event log generation** comprises the assessment of data quality in the original linked dataset and then, the transformation of that dataset into an ‘event log’ data structure -an ordered sequence of individual patient time-stamped events developed in XES format. Typically, each row in the event log will have at least six different pieces of information: timestamp, case identifier, activity label, activity instance identifier, a transactional life cycle stage, and resource identifier; upon those, the log contains any additional attribute characterizing the event (e.g., clinical characteristics of the patients, costs). See here for further details on the event log data model https://www.bupar.net/creating_eventlogs.html#event_data_model

Process discovery (PD) is a technique that aims at using the ‘event log’ modelling processes within an organization. When applied to health care RWD, PD yields the empirical materialization of a clinical pathway in the real world, so how real patients are treated in real conditions, using the ordered sequence of individual patient time-stamped events recorded in any of the data sources. Some evidence has shown the potential of PD in the description and assessment of clinical pathways. [26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31] The stroke pathway will be

captured using the bupaR package and modelled as a Graph [32]. In Annex, Figure 2 shows an example of the outputs of the process discovery step. Subsequent to PD outputs, CONCEPT-STROKE will 1) compare the actual pathways modelled in the previous step with theoretical pathways that a patient with stroke should follow, using conformance checking methodologies; and, 2) analyse the underlying causes for a patient to follow a specific path, using decision mining techniques.

Conformance checking (CC) The inferred pathway (figure 2 in annex) will be compared with the theoretical pathway described in the regional stroke plan manually codified as a Graph, a) using the Log-replay methodology available in ProM, basically, replaying the actual event log data into the manually codified theoretical model to check discrepancies; and, b) using Graph similarity measures, [33, 34] in essence a distance function to assess how two Graphs compare. Finally, as CONCEPT-STROKE will be compiling data from five Spanish health systems, an additional conformance checking analysis will be carried out to compare the different regional pathways with the one closest to the theoretical.

Decision mining (DM) Subsequent to process discovery, each decision point in the Graph (nodes in the figure 2 in annex with more than one outgoing edge) will be captured using the ProM tool. Once the decision points are identified we will infer the underlying factors that would explain why patients follow one path or another within the pathway [35]. For that purpose a multinomial regression will be carried out to estimate the propensity for a specific patient to follow a particular path, considering the theoretical pathway as the reference category. The beta coefficients of the multinomial regression will reflect what individual- or provider- level factors lead the decision towards a particular path. We will use <http://r-statistics.co/Multinomial-Regression-With-R.html>). Note that this propensity, actually a score of propensity, will be inferred from the individual- and provider-level data stored in the event log. As part of the coordinated activities, the Navarrabiomed team will challenge this approach using alternative methods as part of the methodological

objectives; in particular, they will explore Predictive Clustering Trees [36], Classification and Regression Trees[37], and Support Vector Machines [38].

Both the conformance checking and decision mining outputs will be discussed with the group of professionals steering the corresponding Stroke plans in the participating regions. If relevant, the expert input might end up in a new iteration of the process discovery; otherwise, those paths discovered will be used in the next steps. Estimation of outcomes within a path. CONCEPT-STROKE also aims at analyzing the impact of care paths in the survival of patients enduring an acute ischemic stroke (and, in the particular case of Aragon, changes in their functional status). For that purpose, a proportional-hazard regressions will be modelled with the scores of propensity of specific paths being the main independent factor in the prediction of survival at 1 year after admission. We will use <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/survival/survival.pdf>. In turn, as part of the coordination, Navarrabiomed team will additionally test the development of predictive analyses using Predictive Clustering Trees [36] and Naïve Bayes classifiers [39]. In the case of Aragon, predictive models for survival will be enriched using the functional status measured via Rankin score.

Comparative effectiveness in selected paths. Once the outcomes within each path are estimated, CONCEPT-STROKE will estimate the effectiveness of enlargement of the timespan window for thrombectomy (TEC) on patients' survival, as this new policy is expected to increase the number of patients who would benefit from thrombectomy. After drawing the directed acyclic graphs,[40] two approaches will be developed: so, a) the ex-ante ex-post design will compare survival before and after the inception of the new policy; b) the differences in differences design will estimate the differences in survival for those patients treated with thrombectomy, vs. those with a combined therapy (i.e., thrombectomy plus fibrinolysis) vs. those with just fibrinolysis, before and after the inception of the policy. In both cases, after testing the existence of stationary and seasonal effects, Generalized Additive Methods (single-level GAM and multilevel GAMM to infer on the population and on the hospitals, respectively) will allow modelling the trend-change, beyond those time-dependent effects, after the inception of this new policy. We will use <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/mgcv/index.html> and

devel/library/mgcv/html/gamm.html. In the differences in differences design, GAMM will be used after matching those patients with similar propensity scores. We will use <https://sejdemyr.github.io/r-tutorials/statistics/tutorial8.html>.

Economic evaluation in CONCEPT-STROKE The economic analyses in CONCEPT-STROKE will be linked to both, the conformance checking and the analyses on effectiveness. In the former case, a basic costs analysis will be carried out to determine the differences in costs between the actual care pathways and the theoretical pathway, or between the pathways in each of the participant regions. When it comes to the latter, the economic analysis will develop on the incremental cost-effectiveness of the implementation of the new policy of thrombectomy in terms of survival comparing the alternative paths. Economic analyses will be carried out as part of the coordinated activities, led by SESCO.

Ethical aspects

Limitations

Data quality will be assessed in terms of timestamps concordance (those incoherent time-variables will be corrected) and data missingness; in this latter case, inverse probability weighting [41] or k-nearest neighbor (k-NN) imputation [42] will be used. Also related with data richness, the uneven granularity of timestamps available in the event log may be a hindrance to compare pathways across regions. For example, the information on CT scan shots might be missed in Navarre. If so, a decision will be made of the minimum acceptable granularity to carry out meaningful cross-regional comparisons and/or conduct subgroups analyses per region.

There is a difference in the availability of data from the emergency departments, so for example in Aragon there are data available since 2002 while in Catalonia just since 2014. This uneven availability of data should not affect objectives 1 to 5 but will limit the backward period of analysis in objectives 6 to 8, reducing the statistical power in the predictions. Statistical power will be estimated ex post to assess the actual relevance of this potential limitation.

As the incident case definition is based on the admission to the emergency department (A&D), not on the onset of the symptoms, those individuals that do not even arrive to the A&D department (i.e., they die before receiving hospital assistance) and those dying at the A&D department (i.e., there is not CT scan confirmation of the ischemic stroke) won't be considered as incident cases. In the former, there is a risk of selection bias more likely to happen in those cases where distance to the hospital is greater; in order to mitigate that potential bias, distance-time will be used as an instrument in the quasi-experiments. In the latter case, patients dying in the emergency room will be identified using the insured administrative information to see whether

there is a systematic difference with those admitted into the hospital. If so, a sensitivity analysis excluding similar patients will be conducted.

Ethical statement

This study, observational in design, will use retrospective pseudo-anonymized non-identifiable and non-traceable data and will be conducted in accordance with the amended Helsinki Declaration, the International Guidelines for Ethical Review of Epidemiological Studies, the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Spanish laws on data protection and patients' rights. Spanish legislation and ethics' regulations does not require informed consent in retrospective observational studies, where data come from secondary sources and datasets do not include personal information as a consequence of the de-identification procedures developed over the original personal information. Nonetheless, all the CONCEPT projects will be submitted to the Ethical Committee of reference and registered in the US National Library of Medicine registry of observational studies

Balance risk/benefit

It is a population-wide retrospective observational longitudinal study, based on the secondary use of routinely collected social, health and care data from healthcare systems. As such, the intervention already took place preceding the study and there is no risk associated with participating in the study. Potential benefits derived from the study would be applied to the design and development of future pathways of Stroke at population level.

Treatment of personal data

Pseudonymized individual level data will be managed and analyzed within the premises of contributing partners (data hubs, i.e. any institution holding or having access to the data), according to a predefined data model (14) specific to the research question (minimization principle). Data is securely stored within the premises of the participant data hub. Access to this environment will only be provided to researchers involved in the completion of the project. All people authorized to manage the data will be subject to a non-disclosure agreement (NDA). Pseudonymized individual level data will only be processed for uses within the scope of the purposes of the present study and will not be shared with any third party. An analytical pipeline, developed by the project coordination hub, will be implemented within the secured processing environment using the transformed data as input. Extraction of aggregated results from the secured processing environment might be required to complete the purposes of the project involving comparative analysis between countries/regions. All country/region disclosure policies will be respected when producing

and sharing aggregated outputs for comparison or publication. Finally, the scripts of the analytical pipeline and outputs will be published as open source using Zenodo using a CC-BY 4.0 International license following the FAIR principles. In addition, a Data Management Plan (DMP) is produced using ARGOS (OpenAIRE) and is subsequently published in Zenodo. The DMP will continuously be updated as new nodes join to the project (check it at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12794441>).

Healthcare implications

There are no implications for healthcare processes. Results of this study could potentially influence future decisions on public health interventions (i.e., future new pathways of stroke).

Conflict of interest

The researchers declare no conflict of interest.

Chronogram

Duration of this research project is until 30 September 2024.

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Figure 1 Partners participation and exchange across CONCEPT

Figure 2 Process discovery is the basis for conformance checking and decision mining analysis

